

Soil Health for Climate Benefits: Literature Review and Technical Guidance

Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural
Practices

June 30, 2025

About the Technical Advisory Network for Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

The Network emerged from a project of the [Meridian Institute](#) to better align Natural Resource Conservation Service (NRCS) Conservation Practice Standards with the best available science on GHG mitigation. In May 2024, Meridian Institute assembled six technical work groups (TWGs) to provide up-to-date scientific analysis of the impact of conservation practice adoption on GHG emissions and make technical recommendations regarding how best to achieve climate mitigation through those practices. The TWGs were comprised of academic scientists who are well regarded in their chosen field as well as scientists working within nongovernmental organizations focused on one or more of the chosen categories of interest: nutrient management, manure management, enteric methane, soil carbon, agroforestry, and grazing lands.

The technical work groups first identified agricultural practices in the six areas of interest for which evidence indicates considerable potential to reduce GHG emissions based on raw mitigation potential and adoption considerations. In August 2024 Meridian entered into a Contribution Agreement with NRCS to conduct literature reviews of the GHG emissions impacts of 39 practices, individually and in commonly practiced combinations. Meridian staff and TWG chairs and members worked with the NRCS National Discipline Leads to scope the reports and refine technical guidance regarding how best to implement practices to achieve GHG mitigation. The TWGs then conducted literature reviews, first and second-order meta-analyses, and modeling scenarios to identify the circumstances in which there is strong scientific evidence that the agricultural practices identified are likely to have net GHG benefits as well as implementation guidance for maximizing those benefits. The TWGs generated more than a dozen reports, which were delivered to NRCS in June 2025.

With the closing of Meridian Institute in mid-2025, the six technical working groups assembled by Meridian decided to establish the Network to provide a platform for sharing the work undertaken with a diversity of interested stakeholders and to support future collaboration within and/or across technical working groups. Slightly modified versions of the reports delivered to NRCS, such as this report, have been issued publicly by the Network and findings from several groups will be published in academic journals. The Network may also create briefs to summarize findings and technical recommendations for field conservationists and other interested stakeholders.

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Scientific Overview

Assessing the impact of soil health practices on in-field GHG emissions requires consideration of both carbon and nitrous oxide (N₂O). The amount of organic carbon in the soil (SOC) plays an important role in overall soil health, and is a balance over time between 1) inputs of C from crop leaves, stems, and roots, as well as additions of manure, compost, and biochar, and 2) outputs of C, mostly as carbon dioxide (CO₂) from SOC decomposition, but also from burning of crop residues, removal in harvest, and loss through water and wind erosion. While gains of SOC due to changes in management can remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, emissions of N₂O, a potent greenhouse gas (GHG), are also important in cropland soils. Emissions of N₂O are linked to management, especially nitrogen (N) fertilizer, as well as other soil and environmental factors. From the viewpoint of GHG budgeting, relatively small increases in N₂O emissions can reduce or even cancel out any gains in SOC. Therefore, in this technical note we consider both and report on how choices of management affect them individually and in combination.

Methods

LITERATURE REVIEW

In preparation for this technical note, a database search (Scopus, Web of Science, Google Scholar) for peer-reviewed journal articles was carried out using words, terms, acronyms, and abbreviations that included and reflected soil health, soil organic carbon, nitrous oxide, cover crop, conservation crop, conservation cover, reduced and conservation tillage, no-till, and rotation. After refining the many thousands of results, some 300 relevant articles focusing on empirical field studies, including more than 60 meta-analyses, were identified for further review and potential inclusion in a literature review to inform the guidance presented in this document.

MODELING

We used a multi-model ensemble (MME) comprised of eight well-established, process-based cropping systems models to estimate changes in SOC and N₂O emissions for each of the management practices. The MME was validated against long-term field trials and shows greater accuracy and lower uncertainty when compared to its constituent models. The MME was run at 40,000 unique locations and scaled across 934 counties in the US Corn Belt to cover about 114 million acres (about 46 million hectares) of cropland in Illinois, Indiana, Iowa, Kansas, Michigan, Minnesota, Missouri, Nebraska, North Dakota, Ohio, South Dakota, and Wisconsin. Model simulations were performed for 42 years (1980-2022). Details on model types, assumptions, settings, and process, as well as details on field trials used in validation are available from Basso et al. (2025): <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.02.04.636509>.

For the sections below that focus on single management impacts on either SOC or N₂O, we draw information from the literature search. As there are limited field measurements on combined (stacked) management practices and their simultaneous impact on SOC and N₂O, the MME approach primarily is used for these scenarios.

Which Practices can Increase SOC and Reduce N₂O Emissions?

COVER CROPS

Planting cover crops can offer many soil health benefits that vary by location, season, and year. Beyond the scope of this report, these include reducing soil erosion, suppressing weeds and pests, improving water quality, and increasing biodiversity.

DO COVER CROPS INCREASE SOC LEVELS IN USA CROPLAND?

Cover crops can increase levels of SOC by adding more C from their shoots and roots (Van Eerd et al., 2023) and reducing C loss from soil erosion (Huang et al., 2025). Studies that have analyzed multiple cropland fields and research sites in the USA have found that SOC (in the top 30cm) increases on average by about 0.12 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Blanco-Canqui, 2022; Peng et al., 2023).

WHICH FACTORS IMPACT HOW COVER CROPS INCREASE SOC LEVELS IN USA CROPLAND?

Many factors can influence the effect of cover crops on SOC content. In USA cropland soils, major factors include 1) cover crop biomass, 2) duration of cover crop in rotation, 3) soil properties such as clay content and initial SOC content before cover crop introduction, and 4) climate (Table 1).

- 1) Most importantly, the amount of biomass a cover crop can accumulate is directly linked to the amount of C it can return to the soil (through above and below ground residues). Blanco-Canqui, (2022) found that above ground cover crop biomass of at least 2 Mg ha⁻¹ was needed before any noticeable increase in SOC was observed, and at least 6 Mg ha⁻¹ was required for consistent and substantial increases in SOC. Where cover crops have a shorter growing season between late fall planting and early spring termination, such as in cool, temperate regions of the Midwest, this 2 Mg ha⁻¹ of biomass is difficult to achieve. The minimum amount of biomass required before an increase in SOC is observed is also likely to be higher in regions where rainfall is limited, such as the South Central semi-arid prairies. Extending the number of days that a cover crop is actively growing, by prioritizing favorable seasonal conditions in the fall or spring, as opposed to simply maximizing the time between its planting and termination, may be a better management strategy to increase cover crop biomass (e.g., Ruis et al., 2017). Practices to achieve this can include interseeding the cover crop before the main crop is harvested or planting a cover crop in a summer fallow period or after a short-season crop.
- 2) The longer that cover crops are included in a rotation, the greater the likelihood that SOC will accumulate due to their presence. Including cover crops in rotation for at least 5 to 10 years may be most beneficial (Peng et al. 2023; Blanco-Canqui, 2022). Beyond this time SOC levels may increase but not at such a high rate, as soils have natural saturation limits for SOC content.
- 3) Soils with lower initial SOC levels typically show larger gains in SOC after cover crops are introduced. When initial levels of SOC are low (<1%), the accumulation rate of SOC following

cover crop introduction can be two to three times the rate of accumulation compared to when initial SOC levels are intermediate (1-2%), or high (> 2%), respectively (i.e., 0.25 versus 0.12 and 0.08 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹; Blanco-Canqui, 2022). Higher clay content has also been found to lead to larger gains in SOC under cover crops as clay can stabilize (i.e., physically and chemically protect) more organic matter (Peng et al., 2023).

- 4) Patterns of precipitation during the cover crop growing season help determine cover crop biomass, and therefore the potential for SOC gain. For example, increasing rainfall that results in a decrease in soil moisture deficit at a given location can help drive an increase in SOC content when cover crops are planted (Peng et al. 2023).

Table 1. Summary of the effect of various factors on SOC change (0-30 cm depth) due to cover crop (CC) introduction.¹ NT=no-till, RT=reduced tillage, and CT=conventional tillage, in increasing order of intensity. ² Despite trends, there were no significant correlations between SOC gain and texture, MAP, or MAT. ³ Arrow directions and colors represent the directional trend (whether significant or not significant) of the change in SOC due to an increase in the numerical value of the impact factor (NB: for CC type and CC mix vs single, the arrows denote the trend with the categorical variables); a green up arrow denotes a trend for an increase in the gain of SOC, a black horizontal arrow denotes no observable trend in SOC gain, and a red down arrow denotes a trend for a decrease in the gain of SOC. Adapted from Blanco-Canqui, (2022).

Factor	Factor grouping	Comparisons (%) where SOC increases	General trend of SOC to (increasing) factor ³
CC biomass (Mg ha ⁻¹)	<2	0	
	2-6	17	
	>6	71	
CC duration (years)	≤5	14	
	5-10	53	
	>10	54	
Tillage intensity ¹	NT	29	
	RT	17	
	CT	31	
CC type	Legumes	36	
	Grasses	27	
CC mix vs. single (type)	Single species	31	
	Mixes	23	
Soil texture ²	(silty) clay loam, clay	16	
	(silt) loam	37	

	loamy sand, sandy loam	26	
Initial SOC (%)	≤1	64	
	1-2	29	
	>2	20	
MAT (°C) ²	≤15	32	
	>15	24	
MAP (mm) ²	≤500	42	
	500-1000	24	
	>1000	27	

DO COVER CROPS REDUCE N₂O EMISSIONS IN USA CROPLAND?

Cover crops and their management have an impact on all the factors and processes that influence N₂O production and emissions from the soil. These include the amount of mineralizable N and easily decomposable C in the soil, soil microbial communities, soil water content, and soil physical properties. Therefore, emissions of N₂O vary substantially over even short distances within a field and over short time periods, particularly when soil is disturbed or when N is added. Identifying changes in management that reliably reduce N₂O emissions is difficult due to this inherent variability as well as measurement challenges. These challenges are reflected in the mixed results found in literature reviews and analyses, where the introduction of cover crops has been shown to decrease (Muhammad et al. 2019) or increase (Daryanto et al. 2018) N₂O emissions to varying extent or have no overall effect (Basche et al. 2014; Abdalla et al. 2019). Two recent and comprehensive global analyses find a substantial and consistent increase (26% to 30%) in N₂O emissions when cover crops are planted (He et al., 2025; Qiu et al., 2024). This is particularly so under the following conditions 1) when leguminous cover crops are planted, 2) when cover crop residues are incorporated into the soil, 3) under warm or arid climates, or 4) during the first five years after cover crop introduction. Given these and other factors, management to reduce N₂O emissions may include 1) planting non-leguminous cover crops in soils with low initial SOC, 2) maintaining the cover crop in rotation for longer than five years, 3) not applying N fertilizer to the cover crop, and 4) not incorporating cover crop residue into the soil.

TILLAGE

Tillage practices are typically distinguished by the type of equipment used, resulting in varying degrees of soil disturbance and incorporation of surface plant C into deeper layers. Full inversion tillage (FT), often involving a moldboard plow, turns the soil to a depth of at least 6" (15 cm), leaving less than 30% of the surface covered with crop residue. FT can lead to the formation of a compacted layer (clay pan or hardpan) with low hydraulic conductivity, increasingly recognized as a yield-limiting factor—particularly when a wet spring is followed by a dry summer. In such cases, roots concentrate near the surface to access early moisture but struggle to penetrate the restrictive layer during drought conditions. Reduced tillage (RT) disturbs the soil without inversion, using tools such as chisels, sweeps, or discs. No-till (NT)

eliminates inversion altogether, with crops directly seeded into undisturbed soil, typically maintaining over 30% surface residue. NT promotes deeper root growth more quickly than FT, offering a distinct advantage under dry conditions. While we use these broad classifications—FT, RT, and NT—throughout, we acknowledge that specific practices and their effects can vary by region, influenced by local climate, soil type, and cropping systems.

DOES REDUCED TILLAGE OR NO-TILL INCREASE SOC LEVELS IN USA CROPLANDS?

In the plough layer of the soil, NT can increase SOC over FT. An analysis of 302 USA-based studies (Nunes et al. 2020) found that both chisel plough (RT) and NT increase SOC content, by about 14% and 45% respectively, when compared to moldboard plough (FT) in the top 15cm of soil. This analysis also found that these practices need to be maintained for at least three years before noticeable SOC increases occur and are more likely in Alfisols, Inceptisols, Mollisols, and Ultisols.

With deeper soil depths, studies tend to show FT increases SOC below the plough layer (e.g., Blanco-Canqui et al. 2021). Alongside higher SOC in the surface soil, there is often no overall difference between NT and FT practices, although increases where they occur are more likely in sandy soils in cool and warm temperate moist climates (Ogle et al. 2019). Soil may be compacted in NT, increasing apparent SOC stocks, and FT buries SOC in lower layers. While NT is a well-established practice for reducing soil degradation from erosion, helping nutrient cycling, and conserving water in drier climates, overall increases in SOC storage are unlikely and minimal at best.

DOES REDUCED TILLAGE OR NO-TILL DECREASE N₂O EMISSIONS IN USA CROPLAND?

Tillage breaks up large pores and reduces connections between pores, which drives water distribution in the soil and the potential for N₂O production and emissions. On the small scale, N₂O emissions can be altered by soil moisture content, bulk density, soil aeration, soil temperature, soil pH, microbial community composition and enzyme activity, and on the field scale, N management and climate play a role. This complexity is reflected in the inconsistent results found in literature compilations, where NT or RT have been shown to decrease (van Kessel et al. 2013; Li et al. 2023) or increase (Shakoor et al. 2021; Huang et al. 2018) N₂O emissions to varying degrees when compared to FT. Similarly, long-term, site-specific USA-based studies (e.g., Ruis et al., 2022, Bilen et al., 2022, Omonode et al. 2011, Jin et al., 2017, and Gelfand et al. 2016) find that the impact of NT or RT on N₂O emissions is mixed and dependent on the time tillage is practiced and the climate (Table 2).

Table 2. Differences in N₂O fluxes (kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) between no-till (NT) and full inversion tillage (FT) (i.e., FT values subtracted from NT values) after varying practice duration and under different climates. Adapted from Six et al., (2004).

Climate	Year 5	Year 10	Year 20
Humid	3.8	1.1	-4.2
Dry	1.3	0.9	0.0

CONSERVATION CROP ROTATION AND CONSERVATION COVER

The adoption of a conservation crop rotation (growing a sequence of different crops on the same field), or conservation cover practice (growing and maintaining perennial vegetation - not for forage) both increase soil plant cover and can reduce soil erosion, improve nutrient cycling, and conserve soil water, among other benefits (USDA 2014 a, b).

DOES CONSERVATION CROP ROTATION AND/OR CONSERVATION COVER INCREASE SOC LEVELS IN USA CROPLAND?

Compared to cover crops and no-till, far fewer studies have investigated the impact of conservation crop rotation or conservation cover on SOC and N₂O.

CONSERVATION CROP ROTATION

Adding different crops to a monoculture to increase the number of crops in rotation has been shown to increase total soil C content by .04% (i.e., from 2.0% to 2.04% total soil carbon) on average, increasing 0.08% (e.g., from 2.0% to 2.08%) when a legume cover crop is one of the crops included (McDaniel et al., 2014). When crop diversity is increased in a rotation, such as introducing a legume into a grain only rotation, or adding a perennial into an annual only rotation, then SOC content has also been shown to increase, driven by the increase in C input to the soil from the crop biomass. King and Blesh (2017) found that when a cover crop or a perennial crop was added to a grain only rotation, then the SOC concentrations increased by 6% and 13%, respectively.

CONSERVATION COVER

Perennial cropping systems without soil disturbance have been shown to have higher SOC content when compared to annual crop rotations, irrespective of the depth of the soil considered, or whether the soil was tilled (FT, RT) or not (NT). In the USA based analysis of Nunes et al. (2020), perennial cropping systems had SOC contents that were between 1.5 and 2.7 times greater than FT and NT systems across all soil depths to greater than 40 cm.

DOES CONSERVATION CROP ROTATION OR CONSERVATION COVER DECREASE N₂O EMISSIONS IN USA CROPLAND?

CONSERVATION CROP ROTATION

Adding a different crop to a monoculture to increase the number of crops in rotation has a mixed impact on N₂O emissions. Studies in the US Midwest have shown that a corn-soybean rotation can reduce (Adviento-Borbe et al. 2007; Omonode et al., 2011) or have no significant effect (Venterea et al., 2010; Behnke et al. 2018) on overall N₂O emissions when compared to a corn monoculture.

CONSERVATION COVER

Although an overall analysis of USA-based studies to evaluate the impacts of perennials on N₂O emissions is lacking, long-term USA-based site studies show that perennial cropping systems often have much lower N₂O emissions than annual cropping systems. For example, average annual N₂O emissions from perennial crops were between about 6% to 40% of the emissions from annual cropping systems (Gelfand et al., 2016).

Combined Practices

OVERVIEW

While the adoption of single management practices such as no-till or cover crops can improve soil health, the benefits may be greater when practices are combined. The optimal practice mix for a given field or farm will depend on the climate, ecosystem, soil, and other factors.

Farmers who introduce a winter cover crop are more likely than other farmers to introduce another conservation practice, including no-till, with a subsequent crop (Wallander et al., 2021). Continuous no-till is uncommon (Claassen et al., 2018) and for example, no-till is more likely to be implemented in soybean than in corn (Wade and Claassen, 2017).

DO COMBINED PRACTICES INCREASE SOC LEVELS IN USA CROPLAND?

Only a small number of USA-based studies have investigated the impact of combining cover crops and no-till alongside the individual practices of conventional till and no cover crops (Table 3). Overall, these studies indicate that the tillage system effects on the cover crop impacts on SOC change are mixed and can be influenced by N management of the main crop.

Table 3. Effect of tillage system on cover crop impact on soil organic carbon (SOC; 0-20 cm). Full (conventional) tillage (CT), strip till (ST), and no-till (NT). #impact is dependent on the N rate applied to cotton. *References are 1. Sainju et al. (2006), 2. Olson et al. (2014), 3. Mbutia et al. (2015), 4. Clark et al. (2017). Arrow directions and colors represent the directional trend of the change in SOC; a green up arrow denotes a trend for an increase in the gain of SOC, a black horizontal arrow denotes no observable trend in SOC gain, and a red down arrow denotes a trend for a decrease in the gain of SOC. Adapted from Blanco-Canqui, (2022).

Ref.*	Tillage	Study duration (years)	Rotation	Cover Crops	NT impact on SOC
1	CT, ST, NT	3	Cotton-Sorghum	Rye, hairy vetch	
2	CT, NT	3	Wheat-Corn-Soybean	Rye, hairy vetch	
3	CT, NT	31	Cotton (cont.)	Hairy vetch, Wheat	#
4	CT, NT	12	Corn-Soybean	Rye, hairy vetch	

DO COMBINED PRACTICES BOTH INCREASE SOC LEVELS AND REDUCE N₂O EMISSIONS IN USA CROPLAND?

Studies that report long-term data on the simultaneous impact of combined management practices in annual crop rotations on multiple GHG sources and sinks (i.e., SOC and N₂O emissions) are rare. Robertson et al., (2000) did so for a corn-soybean-wheat rotation in the upper Midwest, but given the experimental design, was unable to compare the combined practice (i.e., no-till and reduced N inputs) with their individual practices. Others may exist in the literature but have not been identified. Given this, the modeling (MME) approach is used to present results from these scenarios.

HOW DO WE DETERMINE AND COMPARE THE GHG IMPACT OF MANAGEMENT PRACTICES?

A consistent accounting method is needed to determine the GHG impact and GHG mitigation potential of the different management scenarios. This is done by evaluating the GHG sources and sinks within each scenario in terms of their global warming impact (GWI). For site-based studies, this can involve a comprehensive assessment, determining the GHG emissions associated with fuel use, inputs of fertilizer, pesticide, and seed, as well as biological emissions from the soil (e.g., Gelfand et al. 2013). Here, we use outputs from the multi-model ensemble (MME) to calculate the SOC gain or loss and direct N₂O emissions from the soil. The common unit to which the individual units for each GHG source or sink are converted is the carbon dioxide equivalent (CO₂e). This reflects the amount of CO₂ that would create the same level of global warming as the modeled GHG emissions. Since different GHGs have varying heat-trapping abilities and lifespans in the atmosphere, CO₂e simplifies these differences into a single, comparable value. The equation below can be used to convert N₂O emissions and the change in SOC into units of CO₂e.

Equation 1:

$$GHG_{emission} = E * Con * GWI$$

Where *E* is the emission value (as N₂O-N) or change in SOC (CO₂-C at 0-30 cm soil depth, grouped at the county level across the 114 million acres of USA Midwest cropland) both as kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, *Con* the corresponding conversion factor from N to N₂O (44/28, the ratio of the molecular weight of N₂O compared to the atomic weight of two N atoms) or C to CO₂ (44/12, the ratio of the molecular weight of CO₂ compared to the atomic weight of one C atom), and *GWI*, the 100 year time horizon global warming impact for N₂O (273) or CO₂ (1) (IPCC, 2021). Values for these calculations for four major management practices are shown in Table 4.

WHAT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES PROVIDE GHG MITIGATION?

All the management scenarios investigated show similar N₂O emissions of between 1.35 to 1.52 kg N₂O-N ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, consistent with field observations (e.g., Venterea et al. 2010). Overall, this suggests that over the long-term, tillage type and cover crop presence have limited impact on N₂O emissions, where N fertilizer rates to the main crops in rotation (here, corn and soybean) typically have a larger influence on N₂O emissions (e.g., Gelfand et al. 2016).

The conventionally tilled rotation without a cover crop shows a loss of SOC, averaging 187 kg C ha⁻¹ annually (about 167 pounds C per acre) in the top 30 cm of soil. Planting a cover crop 'counters' this loss, such that there is effectively no change of SOC content over time, due primarily to the overall larger amounts of C returned to the soil from the cover crop biomass. Both no-till scenarios show

modest gains in SOC content, between 164 and 268 kg C ha⁻¹ annually (about 146 to 239 pounds C per acre), in good agreement with long-term field values (e.g., Cordova et al., 2025).

When CO₂e values for SOC and N₂O are combined, we see that conventionally tilled systems are a net source of GHG emissions (negative values for the mean GWI, GHG mitigation value), with the addition of a cover crop reducing this source strength by approximately half (a change from -1.27 to -0.65 Mg CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹). In contrast, the no-till management systems are either CO₂e neutral (effectively neither a source or a sink without a cover crop) or when a cover crop is added, a small net GHG sink (a positive mitigation value of 330 kg CO₂e ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹).

Table 4. Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, Global Warming Impact (GWI; CO₂e) and GHG mitigation (the combined CO₂e for N₂O and SOC, where negative values reflect a net source of GHG emissions and positive values a net sink) of various management practices and their GHG contributions (nitrous oxide [N₂O] emissions from the soil and soil organic carbon [SOC] gain (0-30 cm); negative values reflect a loss of SOC, and positive values a gain in SOC) derived from multi-model ensemble (MME) outputs, averaged (mean) with standard deviation (Std dev) at the county level in 12 states across the USA Midwest. *The scenarios are corn-soybean rotations under conventional (full) tillage (CT), continuous no-till (NT), cover crops (CC, cereal [winter] rye planted before corn and soybean) and their combinations.

Scenario*	N ₂ O emissions			SOC gain			GHG Mitigation
	Mean	Std dev	Mean GWI	Mean	Std dev	Mean GWI	Mean GWI
	kg N ₂ O-N ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹		Mg CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹		Mg CO ₂ e ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹	
CT	1.351	0.392	0.580	- 0.187	0.102	- 0.685	- 1.27
CT + CC	1.500	0.334	0.643	- 0.002	0.090	- 0.008	- 0.65
NT	1.358	0.315	0.582	0.164	0.075	0.600	0.02
NT + CC	1.516	0.327	0.650	0.268	0.068	0.980	0.33

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Appendix: Science Gaps and Recommendations

Critical science gaps need to be filled to improve GHG mitigation research, data collection, and modeling tools to better understand the potential of conservation agriculture practices to mitigate agricultural GHG emissions within and across agricultural sectors. The gaps and needs identified below and associated recommendations are oriented to achieving the goal of enabling GHG mitigation assessment capabilities at the granularity necessary to meaningfully guide agricultural practice adoption and implementation decisions to optimize GHG mitigation across a range of geographic and operational settings. Such assessment capabilities would inform and improve the development and refinement of public and private sector practice standards, policies, programs, and investments to incentivize practices to optimize achievement of GHG mitigation alongside profitability for farmers, cost-effectiveness for incentive and cost-share programs, and achievement of other conservation objectives.

MEASUREMENT AND DATA COLLECTION NEEDS

- Additional field research is needed on combined management practices and their simultaneous impact on SOC and N₂O
- Additional studies are needed on the impact of conservation crop rotation on SOC and N₂O
- Additional studies are needed on the impact of conservation cover on SOC and N₂O
- Data standardization, calibration of available data sets. Focus/guidelines around sampling schemes for on-farm research, with another focusing model calibration.
- There is a need for more studies that aim to understand system variability across a spectrum of implementations.
- There is a need for more even sampling of practices implemented across multiple scenarios (e.g. a variable's complete range), including spatial and temporal sequences.
- Data access: More data is needed to improve models. There needs to be a way for project PIs to submit their data/results and estimate of uncertainty to more centralized databases without always having to wait until the data go through formal journal peer-review. An example would be the highly successful and widely used Ameriflux system hosted by the DOE.

RESEARCH NEEDS

- Research into understanding the combinatorial effects of different soil management practices on GHG mitigation is particularly important for application to on-farm practice implementation scenarios.

MODELING NEEDS

- Model performance depends on availability of high-quality input data. Research and data needs as indicated above can provide more and high-quality data that will help improve estimations and accuracy of models and other quantification tools.
- We need students from more diverse backgrounds to better understand how agriculture and soil carbon modeling might be able to draw lessons from other fields.
- MME is a strong approach that should continue to be explored across different regions.
- Explore the spatial-temporal footprint of modeling itself, along with its limitation, to better understand its implications for policy. Hindcasting, predictive modeling to better understand implications for land use change.
- More research is needed to better understand how to integrate remote sensing into modeling efforts.